

ent papilloma was below the cords. This was dissected out, and there has been no recurrence.

It is impossible to remove papillomata completely by any method of punching or pinching or biting, using the forceps in one hand and some other instrument in the other. It is for this reason, I think, that we have so much recurrence. In the sixteen cases in which I have operated by dissection with suspension there has been no recurrence up to the present time.

DR. HUBBARD, closing the discussion: I think Dr. Lynch has devised the most surgical and precise method of dealing with these growths. All, however, have not the apparatus for this particular work, and so there is a field for the older procedures. I have found it a very useful procedure to put interrupted stitches in the tracheal ring. One must have a free field, snipping off, if necessary, all the isthmus which obscures the view. I usually take up the trachea and put in silkworm gut, about one-third back, through the ring in a child. In other words, I want it as firm as possible. The suture is placed between the cellular tissue and the tracheal ring, one stitch on either side, drawn together, and the ends left long. The ends are brought out on the neck and fixed with adhesive plaster. One can then pull on these and draw the trachea and the larynx forward, getting a glimpse of the lower end of the larynx. Otherwise the curetting is done blindly. Thorough curettage of the larynx can be accomplished by this method with curettes of various sizes and angles. If the papillomata are "ripe" they can be gotten out at the base; those that are in a state of active growth cannot be entirely removed. I always inspect the growth from above prior to curettement.

In using the trichloroacetic acid I simply moisten a small swab, smear with the crystals, and go over the surface with this. The tube is fenestrated, it is inserted in the larynx, and is left there.

I want to call attention again to massage as a factor in producing the condition which brings about the restoration of the normal processes of the larynx. Any simple method like massage is superior to the absolute rest of the larynx induced by the prolonged wearing of the tracheotomy tube.

Some Statistic Observations on Oto-Laryngologic Diseases Among Negroes, Based on Fifteen Hundred Cases. DR. DUNBAR ROY, ATLANTA.

It is surprising how few negroes present themselves for nasal diseases. Out of the total of fifteen hundred, only three hundred and forty-one came for nasal complaints. Spurs and deviations are very rare. The writer has never seen a deviated septum in a full-blooded negro. In the writer's opinion, this is due to two causes. In the development of the maxillary bones you never see a contracted and high arched palate among negroes. This tends to substantiate Mosher's argument as to the importance of the premaxillary ridge in the causation of septum deviations.

Traumatism as a causal factor is rare, because of the protruding brow and soft resilient cartilages externally. Acute inflammation of the accessory sinuses was exceedingly rare, due, in the writer's opinion, to the free ventilation in the nasal cavities. Only chronic necrosing ethmoiditis with polypi occurred more frequently than other chronic sinus diseases. Hay fever occurred in only two cases, and did not differ in

symptoms from that seen in the white race. Atrophic rhinitis was seen in one case only, which would seem to disprove that theory making large nasal passages a predisposing cause for this condition. No case of chronic maxillary abscess was seen. It is a well-known fact that few negroes have bad teeth. Syphilitic lesions were frequent, as also purulent rhinitis in the young, which readily yielded to antisiphilitic treatment of the old regime—i. e., mercury and iodid of potassium.

Pharynx, epipharynx and larynx. There were one hundred and six cases involving these parts, by far the largest percentage. Diphtheria is exceedingly rare in spite of the poor hygienic surroundings of many of these people. Laryngeal tuberculosis occurred only twenty-three times. Laryngeal and pharyngeal syphilis, two hundred and seventy. Adenoids and enlarged faucial tonsils occurred two hundred and ninety-six times, which refutes the statement made several years ago that adenoids are very infrequent among the negroes.

DISCUSSION.

DR. CHARLES W. RICHARDSON, Washington: In the main my observation is in accord with Dr. Roy's, but this is not the case with regard to the apparent immunity of the negro to diphtheria. For a number of years I had charge of the diphtheria ward in the Government Hospital in Washington, which was, in fact, the municipal diphtheria ward. There were practically no negroes in it. I do not remember a case of laryngeal diphtheria in any of the wards. I never intubated a negro child in my whole experience.

My experience is not in accord with Dr. Roy's with regard to the presence of adenoids and enlarged faucial tonsils in negro children. I think some of the worst cases of adenoids I have ever seen and operated on have been in negro children. Some years ago I was inclined to believe that negroes do not have this condition, but latterly, probably in consequence of school inspection, they come into the clinics in great numbers.

Syphilis among negroes is quite general in Washington as well as in Atlanta.

True Myxoma of the Rhinopharynx—Report of Two Cases. DR. VIRGINIUS DABNEY, WASHINGTON.

Extreme rarity of true myxoma anywhere in the body, but especially in the rhinopharynx, leads to report of two cases. Some pathologists reject entirely the term, believing no such pure tumor exists. However, sections show absolute absence of any fibrous elements.

Case 1.—Tumor seen on drawing forward soft palate. Under ether, large adenoid curette fitted over growth which was removed from attachment to the basilar process. No recurrence after ten months.

Case 2.—Two growths found at operation. Only one could be seen at examination; smaller attached to basilar process, larger to posterior ethmoid. Both were divulsed with large adenoid forceps. Patient had had similar growth removed eleven years before. Photographs of growths and of microscopic sections were given.

DISCUSSION.

DR. HARMON SMITH, New York City: This must be the exception which proves the rule. It has been definitely stated by many histologists and